

A faunistic study of Coleoptera of Iran with nine new country records

Studium faunistyczne chrząszczy Iranu, z danymi o dziewięciu gatunkach nowych dla tego kraju

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ABSTRACT. The following paper presents the faunistic study on the Coleoptera of Iran. In total, 41 species in 13 families were collected and identified: Aderidae (1 species), Carabidae (3 spp.), Drilidae (1 sp.), Eucnemidae (5 spp.), Geotrupidae (3 spp.), Glaresidae (1 sp.), Melandryidae (3 spp.), Mycetophagidae (4 spp.), Scarabaeidae (9 spp.), Scaptiidae (1 sp.), Throscidae (4 spp.), Trogidae (4 spp.), and Tetratomidae (2 spp.). Nine species are newly recorded from Iran.

KEY WORDS: beetles, systematic, species diversity, distribution, new records, Iran.

Introduction

The Coleoptera is the largest order in the animal kingdom which includes 40% of all insects and nearly 30% of all animal species (KAZMI & RAMAMURTHY 2004; PARVEZ & SRIVASTAVA 2010). This order includes 166 families and more than 360,000 valid species worldwide (BOUCHARD & al. 2009; LAWRENCE & al. 2011). They are functionally important, being the dominant above-ground invertebrate in pastures and natural grassland when judged by biomass (NICHOLSA 2008; BHARAMAL & al. 2014).

Faunistic surveys on Iranian Coleoptera, which is very diverse, have resulted in several new findings in recent years. Some families were studied rather well and catalogued (e.g., LEGALOV & al. 2010: Curculionoidea; LASON & GHAHARI 2013: Kateretidae and Nitidulidae; BUNALSKI & al. 2014: Scarabaeoidea; BARTOLOZZI & al. 2014: Lucanidae; AZADBAKSH & NOZARI, 2015: Carabidae; GHAHARI & al. 2015: Buprestidae; NOVÁK & GHAHARI 2015: Alleculinae; GHAHARI & Háva 2015: Silphidae; BEAVER & al. 2016: Platypodinae and Scolytinae; JÄCH & al. 2016: Byrrhoidea; PLATIA & GHAHARI 2016: Elateridae; LIU & al. 2016: Bostrichidae; ZAPPI & GHAHARI 2016: Cleridae; MASCAGNI & al. 2016:

Dryopidae and Heteroceridae; THOMAS & GHAHARI 2016: Cucujidae, Laemophloeidae and Silvanidae; MIRUTENKO & GHAHARI 2016: Malachiidae; OTERO & al. 2017: Cryptophagidae; GHAHARI & BOROWIEC 2017: Bruchinae; PERREAU & al. 2017: Leiodidae; RUZZIER & al. 2017: Mordellidae; OTERO & GHAHARI 2017: Latridiidae; ASLAN & GHAHARI 2017: Alticini; GHAHARI & al. 2017: Histeridae; GHAHARI & HÁVA 2017: Dermestidae; VIÑOLAS & GHAHARI 2017: Ptinidae; DARILMAZ & al. 2018: Hydraenidae; Mirutenko & al. 2018: Melyridae, Prionoceridae and Trogossitidae; GENTILI & al. 2018: Hydrophilidae; PLONSKI & GHAHARI 2018: Dasytidae and Rhadalidae; Telnov & GHAHARI 2018: Anthicidae; DARILMAZ & al. 2018: Aquatic Polyphaga; GHAHARI & BARREDA 2019: Ripiphoridae; GHAHARI & NIKODÝM 2018: Glaphyridae; GHAHARI & Campos-Soldini 2019: MELOIDAE; GHAHARI & COLONNELLI 2019a: Attelabidae; GHAHARI & COLONNELLI 2019b: Anthribidae and Nemonychidae; KLAUSNITZER & GHAHARI 2019: Scirtoidea; ASLAN & GHAHARI, 2019: Criocerinae; GHAHARI & BEENEN, 2020: Galerucinae; GHAHARI & COLONNELLI 2020: Brentidae; LYUBARSKY & GHAHARI 2020: Erotylidae; DARILMAZ et al. 2020: Dytiscidae; OTERO & GHAHARI, 2020: Zopheridae; GHAHARI & al. 2020:

Dascilloidea; BOROWIEC & GHAHARI 2021: Cassidinae; DROGVALENKO & GHAHARI 2021: Ciidae).

The purpose of the present study is to enhance the knowledge on the species diversity and distribution of the Coleoptera fauna of Iran, as well as to introduce the new country records.

Material and methods

The specimens herein presented were collected using, among others, sweep nets and light traps from different regions in Iran during various field surveys. All the collected specimens were put in alcohol (ethanol 80%) and identified by the authors and other authorized coleopterists. Additionally, several specimens from the insect collections preserved in the Islamic Azad University (Qaemshahr, Science & Research, and Garmsar Branches) and Tehran Jurassic Park were reexamined, which data have also been included in this paper. Most of the specimens are preserved in the collections of the fifth and sixth author, and a few others in the collections of the determiners. The classification, nomenclature, and distributional data suggested by LÖBL & SMETANA (2007, 2008), and LÖBL & LÖBL (2016, 2017) have been followed. The chorotypes used in this paper, are described as below:

- "Caucasus" is a region between the Black Sea and the Caspian Sea, mainly comprising Armenia, Azerbaijan, Georgia, and parts of Southern Russia;
- "Transcaspia" is an old name for the region lying to the east of the Caspian Sea in Central Asia;
- "Turkestan" also spelled Turkistan, is a historical region in Central Asia, corresponding to the regions of Transoxiana (eastern Uzbekistan, Western Tajikistan, parts of Southern Kazakhstan, parts of Turkmenistan and Southern Kyrgyzstan) and Xinjiang (an autonomous region of the People's Republic of China (PRC), located in the northwest of the country at the crossroads of Central Asia and East Asia).

Results

In the following paper, 41 species from 13 families were collected and identified from different regions of Iran. Nine species (marked with an asterisk *) are newly recorded from Iran: *Anaspis (Anaspis) pulicaria* A. COSTA, 1854, *Berginus tamarisci* WOLLASTON, 1854, *Drilus fulvitaris* BAUDI di SELVE, 1872, *Eulagius irregularis* REITTER, 1888, *Eustrophus dermestoides* FABRICIUS, 1792, *Mycetophagus (Ulolendus) ciscaucasicus* SEMENOV, 1899, *Orchesia (Orchesia) micans* PANZER, 1793, *Orchesia (Clinocara) undulata* KRAATZ, 1853 and *Phloiотrya (Phloiотrya) teraw* HAMPE, 1850.

Aderidae WINKLER, 1927

Otolelus semiobscurus PIC, 1893

Distribution: Georgia, Russia (South European Territory), Iran, "Caucasus", "Turkestan".

Material examined: East Azarbaijan prov., Arasbaran Forest, VIII 2012, 2 exx.

Carabidae LATREILLE, 1802

Harpalus (Harpalus) hospes hospes STURM, 1818

Distribution: Albania, Austria, Bulgaria, Czech Republic, Greece, Hungary, Iran, Kazakhstan, Macedonia, Moldova, Romania, Russia (South European Territory), Serbia, Slovakia, Slovenia, Turkey, Ukraine.

Material examined: Golestan prov., Golestan National Park, VI 2015, 2 exx.

Ophonus (Metophonus) cordatus
(DUFTSCHMID, 1812)

Distribution: Albania, Algeria, Armenia, Austria, Belgium, Bosnia-Herzegovina, Bulgaria, Croatia, Czech Republic, France, Great Britain, Georgia, Greece, Hungary, Iran, Italy, Kazakhstan, Macedonia, Moldova, Montenegro, Morocco, Netherlands, Poland, Romania, Russia (South European Territory, West Siberia), Serbia, Slovakia, Slovenia, Spain, Switzerland, Turkmenistan, Turkey, Ukraine.

Material examined: Mazandaran prov., Galogah (Khoshroodpey Forest), V 2016, 3 exx.

Scybalicus oblongiusculus (DEJEAN, 1829)

Distribution: Algeria, Bosnia-Herzegovina, Bulgaria, Croatia, France, Greece, Iran, Italy, Malta, Morocco, Portugal, Slovenia, Spain, Tunisia, Turkey.

Material examined: Mazandaran prov., Amol (Chelav), V 2013, 2 exx.

Drilidae BLANCHARD, 1845

**Drilus fulvitaris* BAUDI di SELVE, 1872

Distribution: "Caucasus".

Material examined: East Azarbaijan prov., Arasbaran Forest, VIII 2012, 1 ex. New record for Iran.

Eucnemidae ESCHSCHOLTZ, 1829

Eucnemis capucina AHRENS, 1812

Distribution: Algeria, Austria, Belgium, Bosnia-Herzegovina, Belarus, Croatia, Czech Republic, Denmark, Finland, France, Germany, Hungary, Iran, Italy, Latvia, Liechtenstein, Lithuania,

Luxembourg, Netherlands, Poland, Romania, Russia (Central European Territory, West Siberia), Slovakia, Spain, Sweden, Switzerland.

Material examined: Guilan prov., Siahkal, IX 2014, 2 exx.

Farsus dubius PILLER & MITTERPACHER, 1783

Distribution: Austria, Czech Republic, France, Hungary, Iran, Italy, Romania, Russia (South European Territory), Serbia and Montenegro, Spain, Syria.

Material examined: West Azarbaijan prov., Naqadeh (Hassanloo), VII 2010, 3 exx.

Microrhagus pygmaeus FABRICIUS, 1792

Distribution: Belgium, Bosnia-Herzegovina, Bulgaria, Belarus, Czech Republic, Denmark, Estonia, Finland, France, Germany, Great Britain, Hungary, Iran, Italy, Latvia, Lithuania, Netherlands, Norway, Poland, Romania, Russia (Central and North European Territory), Slovakia, Sweden, Switzerland.

Material examined: East Azarbaijan prov., Arasbaran Forest, VIII 2012, 2 exx.

Phyllocerus elateroides MÉNÉTRIÉS, 1832

Distribution: Greece, Iran, "Caucasus".

Material examined: Ardabil prov., Aslanduz (Qeshlagh Ghahramanloo), VIII 2011, 1 ex.

Rhacopus sahlbergi MANNERHEIM, 1823

Distribution: Austria, Bosnia-Herzegovina, Belarus, Croatia, Estonia, Finland, France, Germany, Greece, Hungary, Iran, Italy, Latvia, Mongolia, Poland, Romania, Russia (Central and North European Territory, West Siberia), Slovakia, Sweden.

Material examined: East Azarbaijan prov., Arasbaran Forest, VIII 2012, 1 ex.

Geotrupidae LATREILLE, 1802

Anoplotrupes stercorosus SCRIBA, 1791

Distribution: Albania, Andorra, Austria, Belgium, Bosnia-Herzegovina, Bulgaria, Belarus, Croatia, Czech Republic, Denmark, Estonia, Finland, France, Germany, Great Britain, Georgia, Greece, Hungary, Iran, Ireland, Italy, Kosovo, Latvia, Liechtenstein, Lithuania, Luxembourg, Macedonia, Moldova, Montenegro, Netherlands, Norway, Poland, Portugal, Romania, Russia (Central, North and South European Territory, East and West Siberia), Serbia, Slovakia, Slovenia, Spain, Sweden, Switzerland, Turkey, Ukraine.

Material examined: Mazandaran prov., Behshahr (Koohestan), IX 2014, 2 exx.

Odonteus armiger SCOPOLI, 1772

Distribution: Armenia, Austria, Azerbaijan, Belgium, Bosnia-Herzegovina, Bulgaria, Belarus, Croatia, Czech Republic, Denmark, Estonia, France, Great Britain, Germany, Greece, Hungary, Iran, Italy, Kazakhstan, Latvia, Lithuania, Luxembourg, Macedonia, Moldova, Netherlands, Poland, Romania, Russia (Central and South European Territory), Serbia, Slovakia, Slovenia, Spain, Sweden, Switzerland, Turkey, Ukraine.

Material examined: Mazandaran prov., Ramsar (Dalkhani Forest), VIII 2017, 3 exx.

Trypocopriss vernalis vernalis LINNAEUS, 1758

Distribution: Albania, Andorra, Austria, Belgium, Bosnia-Herzegovina, Bulgaria, Belarus, Croatia, Czech Republic, Denmark, Estonia, Finland, France, Germany, Great Britain, Greece, Hungary, Iran, Ireland, Italy, Kosovo, Latvia, Liechtenstein, Lithuania, Luxembourg, Macedonia, Moldova, Montenegro, Netherlands, Norway, Poland, Romania, Russia (Central, North and South European Territory), Serbia, Slovakia, Slovenia, Spain, Sweden, Switzerland, Turkey, Ukraine.

Material examined: Qazvin prov., Moalem Kelayeh, VI 2018, 2 exx.

Glaresidae KOLBE, 1905

Glaresis rufa ERICHSON, 1848

Distribution: Azerbaijan, Austria, Bulgaria, Greece, Hungary, Iran, Kazakhstan, Poland, Romania, Russia (South European Territory), Serbia, Slovakia, Ukraine.

Material examined: West Azarbaijan prov., Myandoab (Qarehghozlu), VIII 2010, 1 ex.

Melandryidae LEACH, 1815

**Phloiodytes (Phloiodytes) teraw* HAMPE, 1850

Distribution: Armenia, Austria, Azerbaijan, Belgium, Croatia, Czech Republic, France, Georgia, Germany, Great Britain, Greece, Hungary, Italy, Netherlands, Romania, Russia (South European Territory), Slovakia, Spain, Switzerland, Ukraine.

Material examined: West Azarbaijan prov., Myandoab (Qarehghozlu), VIII 2010, 2 exx. New record for Iran.

**Orchesia (Clinocara) undulata* KRAATZ, 1853

Distribution: Albania, Algeria, Armenia, Austria, Azerbaijan, Belgium, Bosnia-Herzegovina, Bulgaria, Belarus, Croatia, Czech Republic, Denmark, Finland, France, Georgia, Germany, Great Britain, Hungary, Ireland, Italy, Latvia, Moldova, Netherlands, Norway, Poland, Romania, Russia (Central and South European Territory, East Siberia), Serbia and Montenegro, Slovakia, Slovenia, Spain, Sweden, Switzerland, Ukraine.

Material examined: Chaharmahal & Bakhtiari prov., Brojen (Seif-Abd), VI 2014, 2 exx. New record for Iran.

**Orchesia (Orchesia) micans* PANZER, 1793

Distribution: Albania, Algeria, Armenia, Austria, Azerbaijan, Belgium, Bosnia-Herzegovina, Bulgaria, Belarus, Croatia, Czech Republic, Denmark, Estonia, Finland, France, Georgia, Germany, Great Britain, Greece, Hungary, Ireland, Italy, Latvia, Moldova, Netherlands, Norway, Poland, Romania, Russia (Central, North and South European Territory, West Siberia), Serbia and Montenegro, Slovakia, Slovenia, Spain, Sweden, Switzerland, Tunisia, Turkey, Ukraine.

Material examined: Hamadan prov., Nahavand, VIII 2016, 3 exx. New record for Iran.

Mycetophagidae LEACH, 1815

**Berginus tamarisci* WOLLASTON, 1854

Distribution: Albania, Algeria, Austria, Belgium, Bosnia-Herzegovina, Bulgaria, Croatia, Czech Republic, Egypt, England, France, Germany, Georgia, Greece, Hungary, Indonesia: Java, Israel, Italy, Madeira Is., Malta, Morocco, Nigeria, Poland, Portugal, Romania, Russia, Slovakia, Slovenia, Spain, Sweden, Switzerland, Tunisia, Turkey, Ukraine (Crimea).

Material examined: East Azarbaijan prov., Arasbaran Forest, VIII 2012, 2 exx. New record for Iran.

**Eulagius irregularis* REITTER, 1888

Distribution: Armenia, Azerbaijan, Georgia, Russia (South European Territory).

Material examined: West Azarbaijan province, Oshnavieh (Khaled-Abad), VI 2014, 2 exx. New record for Iran.

Mycetophagus (Mycetoxides) fulvicollis
FABRICIUS, 1792

Distribution: Albania, Armenia, Austria, Azerbaijan, Belgium, Belarus, Bosnia-Herzegovina, Bulgaria,

Croatia, Czech Republic, Denmark, Estonia, Finland, France, Georgia, Germany, Great Britain, Greece, Hungary, Iran, Italy, Kazakhstan, Latvia, Lithuania, Moldova, Mongolia, Montenegro, Norway, Poland, Portugal, Romania, Russia (Central, North and South European Territory, East and West Siberia, Far East), Serbia, Slovakia, Slovenia, Spain, Sweden, Switzerland, Turkey, Ukraine.

Material examined: Qazvin prov., Moalem Kelayeh, VI 2012, 3 exx.

**Mycetophagus (Ulolendus) ciscaucasicus*
SEMENOV, 1899

Distribution: Armenia, Azerbaijan, Georgia, Russia (South European Territory), Turkey, Ukraine.

Material examined: Ardabil prov., Aslanduz (Qeshlagh Ghahramanloo), VIII 2011, 1 ex. New record for Iran.

Scarabaeidae LATREILLE, 1802

Amphimallon leuthneri REITTER, 1902

Distribution: Iran, Syria, Turkey.

Material examined: Kermanshah prov., Paveh (Khanghah), V 2016, 1 ex.

Aplidia tarsensis KRAATZ, 1882

Distribution: Iran, Lebanon, Syria, Turkey.

Material examined: West Azarbaijan prov., Myandoab (Qarehghozlu), VIII 2010, 1 ex.

Chaetopteroptia syriaca BURMEISTER, 1844

Distribution: Iran, Israel, Syria, Turkey.

Material examined: Kermanshah prov., Paveh (Khanghah), V 2016, 1 ex.

Onthophagus (Palaeonthophagus) fissicornis
(STEVEN, 1809)

Distribution: Albania, Armenia, Azerbaijan, Bulgaria, Croatia, Georgia, Greece, Iran, Iraq, Israel, Macedonia, Moldova, Montenegro, Romania, Russia (South European Territory), Serbia, Syria, Turkey, Turkmenistan, Ukraine.

Material examined: Qazvin prov., Moalem Kelayeh, VI 2012, 2 exx.

Onthophagus (Palaeonthophagus) sacharovskii
OLSOUFIEFF, 1918

Distribution: Armenia, Georgia, Iran, Turkey.

Material examined: East Azarbaijan prov., Jolfa, IX 2016, 2 exx.

Paroniticellus festivus (STEVEN, 1809)

Distribution: Armenia, Azerbaijan, Georgia, Iran, Russia (South European Territory), Turkey, Turkmenistan.

Material examined: Guilan prov., Siahkal, VII 2010, 3 exx.

Pleurophorus apicipennis REITTER, 1892

Distribution: Afghanistan, China, Iran, Kyrgyzstan, Kazakhstan, Pakistan, Tajikistan, Turkey, Turkmenistan, Uzbekistan.

Material examined: Razavi Khorasan prov., Quchan (Emam-Gholi), VIII 2017, 1 ex.

Protaetia (Netocia) asiatica (FALDERMANN, 1835)

Distribution: Armenia, Azerbaijan, Georgia, Iran.

Material examined: East Azarbaijan prov., Azarshahr (20 km E Nadilu), VIII 2004, 2 exx.

Tanyproctus (Tanyproctus) persicus (MENETRIES, 1832)

Distribution: Azerbaijan, Georgia, Iran.

Material examined: East Azarbaijan prov., Arasbaran Forest, VIII 2012, 1 ex.

Scraptiidae MULSANT, 1856**Anaspis (Anaspis) pulicaria* A. COSTA, 1854

Distribution: Albania, Algeria, Austria, Azerbaijan, Bosnia-Herzegovina, Bulgaria, Croatia, France, Georgia, Germany, Great Britain, Georgia, Hungary, Israel, Italy, Macedonia, Morocco, Netherlands, Poland, Portugal, Russia (North European Territory), Spain, Switzerland, Tunisia, Ukraine.

Material examined: Hamadan prov., Malayer (Qalae Babakhan), VIII 2018, 2 exx. New record for Iran.

Throscidae LAPORTE, 1840*Trixagus duvalii* BONVOULOIR, 1859

Distribution: Austria, Cyprus, Czech Republic, Denmark, Finland, France, Germany, Great Britain, Greece, Hungary, Iran, Italy, Poland, Romania, Russia (South European Territory), Slovakia, Slovenia, Spain, Sweden.

Material examined: Mazandaran prov., Kelardasht, VII 2013, 2 exx.

Trixagus gracilis WOLLASTON, 1854

Distribution: Algeria, Armenia, Austria, Azores, Bosnia-Herzegovina, Bulgaria, Croatia, Cyprus, France, Germany, Great Britain, Greece, Hungary,

Iran, Italy, Madeira, Moldova, Morocco, Portugal, Switzerland, Turkey.

Material examined: East Azarbaijan prov., Kaleibar, VII 2002, 5 exx.

Trixagus perversus COBOS, 1958

Distribution: Afghanistan, Iran, Turkmenistan.

Material examined: Northern Khorasan prov., Raz, IV 2013, 1 ex.

Trixagus turkestanus REITTER, 1921

Distribution: Azerbaijan, Iran, "Turkestan", "Transcaspia".

Material examined: West Azarbaijan prov., Oshnavieh (Khaled-Abad), VI 2014, 1 ex.

Trogidae MACLEAY, 1819*Trox litoralis* PITTINO, 1991

Distribution: Albania, Algeria, Austria, Bosnia-Herzegovina, Croatia, Greece, Iran, Italy, Malta, Montenegro, Turkey.

Material examined: East Azarbaijan prov., Arasbaran Forest, VIII 2012, 1 ex.

Trox morticinii PALLAS, 1781

Distribution: China, Iran, Kazakhstan, Kyrgyzstan, Russia (South European Territory, East and West Siberia), Turkmenistan.

Material examined: Northern Khorasan prov., Shirvan (Eslam-Abad Karkhaneh Ghand), VIII 2015, 2 exx.,

Trox perrisii FAIRMAIRE, 1868

Distribution: Algeria, Austria, Belgium, Belarus, Croatia, Czech Republic, France, Germany, Hungary, Iran, Italy, Morocco, Poland, Portugal, Russia (Central and South European Territory), Slovakia, Slovenia, Spain, Switzerland, Turkey, Ukraine.

Material examined: East Azarbaijan prov., Khomarloo, VII 2009, 2 exx.

Trox sordidatus BALTHASAR, 1936

Distribution: Bulgaria, Croatia, Greece, Iran, Syria, Turkey.

Material examined: Kordestan prov., Bijar (Khosrow-Abad), VII 2014, 1 ex.

Tetratomidae BILLBERG, 1820

**Eustrophus dermestoides* FABRICIUS, 1792

Distribution: Austria, Bosnia-Herzegovina, Bulgaria, Belarus, Croatia, Czech Republic, Finland, France, Germany, Greece, Hungary, Italy, Latvia, Lithuania, Macedonia, Poland, Romania, Slovakia, Slovenia, Spain, Switzerland, Turkey, Ukraine.

Material examined: Zanjan prov., Abhar (Sonbol-Abad), VI 2015, 2 exx. New record for Iran.

Tetratoma fungorum Fabricius, 1790

Distribution: Armenia, Austria, Azerbaijan, Belgium, Croatia, Czech Republic, Denmark, Estonia, Finland, France, Georgia, Germany, Great Britain, Hungary, Iran, Ireland, Italy, Latvia, Liechtenstein, Lithuania, Macedonia, Moldova, Netherlands, Norway, Poland, Romania, Russia (South European Territory), Serbia and Montenegro, Slovakia, Spain, Sweden, Switzerland, Turkey, Ukraine.

Material examined: Guilan prov., Masal (km 4 Masal-Khalkhal Road), VIII 2004, 3 exx.

Discussion

In the present faunistic study, 41 species from 32 genera and 13 families (Aderidae, Carabidae, Drilidae, Eucnemidae, Geotrupidae, Glaresidae, Melandryidae, Mycetophagidae, Scarabaeidae, Scaptiidae, Throscidae, Trogidae, and Tetratomidae) were collected from different regions of Iran. The finding of nine new country records in this research, together with several catalogues of the Iranian Coleoptera (see references), indicate that the fauna of Coleoptera is very diverse in Iran, and thus it still requires further examination. Iran is the 18th largest country in the world and comprises various geographical areas and ecosystems (ZEHZAD & al. 2002; HAKIMZADEH KHOEI & al. 2011); therefore, new data (new country records, new species, and new distributional data) are expected to be found during systematic faunistic researches.

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STRESZCZENIE

Na podstawie analizy materiału badawczego pochodzącego z badań faunistycznych prowadzonych w różnych prowincjach Iranu podano nowe informacje dotyczące rozmieszczenia 41 gatunków chrząszczy (Coleoptera). Reprezentują one 32 rodzaje należące do 13 rodzin: Aderidae, Carabidae, Drilidae, Eucnemidae, Geotrupidae, Glaresidae, Melandryidae, Mycetophagidae, Scarabaeidae, Scaptiidae, Throscidae, Trogidae i Tetratomidae.

Dziewięć z wykazanych gatunków jest nowych dla Iranu. Są to: *Anaspis (Anaspis) pulicaria* COSTA, 1854, *Berginus tamarisci* WOLLASTON, 1854, *Drilus fulvitaris* BAUDI, 1872, *Eulagius irregularis* REITTER, 1888, *Eustrophus dermestoides* FABRICIUS, 1792, *Mycetophagus (Ulolendus) ciscaucasicus* SEMENOV, 1899, *Orchesia (Orchesia) micans* PANZER, 1793, *Orchesia (Clinocara) undulata* KRAATZ, 1853 i *Phloiodytra (Phloiodytra) teraw* HAMPE, 1850.

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